

ON THE COMPARISON OF MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF PA66GF30 AND PA6TGF40 SHORT FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS

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Abstract

Short fiber reinforced plastics are widely used in different industries including but not limited to automotive, aviation and heating. Their relatively good strength and low weight makes them the main choice for applications where it is required to endure harsh conditions such as elevated temperature, humidity and creep loads. In addition, their capability of easier forming into complex geometries with injection molding allowed them to be used as components of combi boilers that are in contact with drinking water where temperature levels up to 60 °C are noted. Polyamide 66 with 30% glass fiber content (PA66GF30) has a proven background in such applications. However, changes in drinking water regulations in EU by Drinking Water Ordinance dictates to reduce PFAS (per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances), resulting in suppliers that produce parts in contact with drinking water to investigate alternative materials which indicate similar or better endurance when subjected to working condition loads. For this purpose, temperature resistant polyphthalamide (PA6T/6I) with 40% glass fiber content (PA6TGF40) with three different dominant fiber angles were tested using Shimadzu AG-X conventional testing equipment at three different strain rates according to ISO 527. Results showed that mechanical behavior of alternative material is very close to PA66GF30 with significant strain rate dependent behavior even at quasi-static strain rate regime. Also, it was observed that dominant fiber angle effects the mechanical properties, with 0° fiber orientation indicating highest stress values during tensile tests. It should be noted that further study must be conducted to observe the effect of thermal aging on stress-strain behavior of PA6TGF40. The authors would like to thank Bosch Termoteknik Isıtma ve Klima Sanayi Ticaret A.Ş. for their contributions to this study.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Fiber Reinforced Plastics, Strain Rate, Tensile Test